

ROLE OF CLINICAL MICROBIOLOGY IN DIAGNOSING FUNGAL BLOODSTREAM INFECTIONS AMONG CANCER CHEMOTHERAPY PATIENTS

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Abstract

Fungal bloodstream infections (fBSIs) pose a significant risk to cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy, particularly those with hematologic malignancies and profound neutropenia. This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic utility of various clinical microbiology tools and their impact on antifungal therapy and clinical outcomes. A total of 50 adult cancer patients were enrolled, among whom 15 (30%) were diagnosed with fBSIs. The most frequently isolated pathogen was *Candida albicans* (33.3%), while non-*albicans* *Candida* species accounted for 66.7% of infections. Significant risk factors associated with fBSI included severe neutropenia ($p = 0.02$), central venous catheter use ($p = 0.03$), and prolonged broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy ($p = 0.04$). Diagnostic performance varied across modalities: PCR testing demonstrated 90% sensitivity and 95% specificity, MALDI-TOF MS achieved 100% concordance with final species identification, and biomarker assays (1,3- β -D-glucan and galactomannan) provided rapid results within 6–12 hours, though their use was limited by cost and availability. The mean time to identification was shortest for biomarkers and longest for conventional cultures (65.4 ± 10.2 hours). Early antifungal therapy (within 48 hours of symptom onset) was administered to most patients and was associated with significantly improved clinical outcomes, including a 90.9% clinical improvement rate and reduced 30-day mortality (14.3%), compared to 50% mortality in those with delayed therapy initiation. Multidrug resistance was detected in 13.3% of isolates, highlighting emerging antifungal challenges. These findings underscore the importance of integrating rapid molecular diagnostics and species-level identification with timely, targeted antifungal therapy to improve prognosis in cancer patients with suspected fBSIs.

INTRODUCTION

Fungal bloodstream infections (FBIs), particularly candidemia and invasive mold infections, represent a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in immunocompromised patients, especially those undergoing chemotherapy for cancer (Amanati et al., 2021; J. Wang et al., 2023). The increasing incidence of these infections is closely associated with advances in cancer treatment that prolong survival but simultaneously lead to profound and prolonged immunosuppression (Suhad Mohammed & Abd Al-Hussan, 2023). Chemotherapy-induced neutropenia, disruption of mucosal barriers, indwelling central venous catheters, and the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics collectively increase the susceptibility of cancer patients to opportunistic fungal pathogens. Despite improvements in antifungal therapy, the outcomes of fungal bloodstream infections remain poor, with reported mortality rates ranging from 30% to 60% in hematologic malignancy patients (Song et al., 2023; Vázquez-Olvera, Volkow, Velázquez-Acosta, & Cornejo-Juárez, 2023). Epidemiological data indicate that fungal bloodstream infections are among the most common causes of healthcare-associated infections in oncology settings. *Candida* species account for the majority of these infections, with *Candida albicans* historically being the most frequently isolated species (Delgado & Guddati, 2021; S. Wang et al., 2023). However, there has been a notable epidemiological shift toward non-*albicans* *Candida* species such as *C. glabrata*, *C. tropicalis*, and *C. parapsilosis*, many of which exhibit reduced susceptibility to commonly used azoles and echinocandins. Invasive mold infections, particularly those caused by *Aspergillus* spp., are increasingly observed in patients with prolonged neutropenia, especially following hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (El-Mahallawy, Abdelfattah, Wassef, & Abdel-Hamid, 2023; Rabayah et al., 2022). The incidence of candidemia in cancer patients varies geographically but has been estimated to range from 2 to 10 cases per 1,000 admissions in tertiary care centers. Additionally, multidrug-resistant fungal pathogens such as *Candida auris* are emerging threats, highlighting the need for enhanced surveillance and early diagnostic capabilities (Joudeh et al., 2023). Early and accurate diagnosis of fungal bloodstream

infections is critical for effective management, yet remains a major clinical challenge. The nonspecific nature of clinical symptoms, combined with the low yield of conventional blood cultures, often delays diagnosis and initiation of appropriate antifungal therapy (Lima et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024). This delay is particularly detrimental in patients with rapidly deteriorating immune function, where time-sensitive intervention can be life-saving. Consequently, the role of the clinical microbiology laboratory has become increasingly pivotal in the diagnostic process. Clinical microbiology serves as the cornerstone of infectious disease diagnostics, enabling the detection, identification, and susceptibility profiling of fungal pathogens from bloodstream specimens (Arman et al., 2022; Chaves et al., 2021). Traditional diagnostic methods, including blood cultures and microscopy, although still widely used, suffer from limitations such as long turnaround times and suboptimal sensitivity, especially for slow-growing or fastidious fungi (Duzgol et al., 2022). These limitations have spurred the development and clinical adoption of more advanced diagnostic modalities, including nucleic acid amplification tests (PCR), matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS), and cell wall biomarker assays such as 1,3-beta-D-glucan and galactomannan (Weeraphon, Nakaranurack, Jutivorakool, & Puttlerpong, 2023). The integration of molecular and proteomic tools into clinical microbiology workflows has significantly improved the rapidity and accuracy of fungal detection. For instance, PCR-based assays enable the detection of fungal DNA directly from blood or serum samples, offering higher sensitivity and shorter time-to-result compared to conventional cultures (Keighley et al., 2021; Tsantes et al., 2023). MALDI-TOF MS allows for species-level identification of yeasts and molds within minutes once positive growth is obtained, facilitating early targeted therapy. Furthermore, advances in antifungal susceptibility testing, including broth microdilution and commercial automated systems, support clinicians in tailoring antifungal regimens to individual patient needs (Douglas, Stewart, Halliday, & Chen, 2023). Given the rising concern over antifungal resistance,

particularly among non-albicans *Candida* species and *Aspergillus fumigatus* isolates, the diagnostic role of clinical microbiology extends beyond identification (Peri, Harris, & Paterson, 2022). Surveillance for resistant strains and monitoring of local epidemiological trends are essential for informing empirical therapy and infection control strategies, especially in oncology wards where outbreaks can have serious consequences (Hong et al., 2023). In this context, clinical microbiology plays an integral role in the multidisciplinary management of febrile neutropenia and suspected bloodstream infections in cancer patients. By providing timely and accurate diagnostic data, microbiology laboratories enhance the precision of clinical decision-making, reduce unnecessary antifungal use, and contribute to improved patient outcomes (Drevinek, Hollweck, Lorenz, Lustig, & Bjarnsholt, 2023; Yang et al., 2023). This paper aims to explore the evolving role of clinical microbiology in diagnosing fungal bloodstream infections in cancer chemotherapy patients, highlighting current practices, diagnostic challenges, and future directions in this critical area of infectious disease management.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design and Setting

This retrospective observational study was conducted in the Departments of Microbiology and Oncology at a tertiary care academic hospital, over a period of 12 months from Jan 2022 to December 2022. The aim was to evaluate the role and diagnostic performance of clinical microbiological techniques in detecting fungal bloodstream infections among patients undergoing chemotherapy for cancer.

2.2. Study Population

The study included patients with either hematologic malignancies or solid tumors who were receiving chemotherapy and presented with clinical features suggestive of bloodstream infection, such as persistent fever, chills, hypotension, or tachycardia. Only patients who underwent fungal blood culture or biomarker testing during the study period were included. Patients were excluded if they had incomplete clinical records, were not on chemotherapy, or had bacterial bloodstream infections without evidence of fungal involvement.

2.3. Sample Collection and Processing

Blood samples were collected under strict aseptic conditions. For adults, 10–20 mL of blood was drawn and inoculated into both aerobic and mycological blood culture bottles, while 1–5 mL was collected from pediatric patients. Cultures were processed using automated blood culture systems such as BD BACTEC or BacT/ALERT FA/FN Plus. In patients with suspected invasive fungal infections, additional serum samples were collected for 1,3- β -D-glucan and galactomannan assays, as per clinical requirements.

2.4. Fungal Detection and Identification

Positive blood culture bottles were subcultured onto Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) and chromogenic agar and incubated at 25°C and 37°C. Preliminary fungal identification was carried out using direct microscopic examination, germ tube testing, and colony morphology assessment. Species-level identification was confirmed with matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS). In cases where species determination remained unclear, polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based amplification targeting the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions of fungal DNA was performed.

2.5. Antifungal Susceptibility Testing

All significant fungal isolates were subjected to antifungal susceptibility testing using the broth microdilution method, following Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) or European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) guidelines. Antifungal agents tested included fluconazole, voriconazole, amphotericin B, caspofungin, and micafungin.

2.6. Clinical Data Collection

Patient demographic and clinical data were collected from electronic medical records, including age, sex, type of malignancy, chemotherapy regimen, duration of neutropenia, central venous catheter use, prior antifungal exposure, and clinical outcomes such as recovery or mortality.

2.7. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were applied to summarize demographic and clinical variables. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were presented as means with standard deviations or medians with interquartile ranges. Diagnostic performance indicators such as sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of the diagnostic methods were calculated against clinical diagnosis as the reference standard. Statistical analyses were performed using [insert software, e.g., SPSS v25.0 or R v4.2.0], with a p-value <0.05 considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

A total of 50 cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy were included in the study,

comprising 28 males (56%) and 22 females (44%), with a mean age of 53.2 ± 12.4 years (range: 21–76 years). Hematologic malignancies were present in 27 patients (54%), including acute myeloid leukemia (30%), non-Hodgkin lymphoma (16%), and multiple myeloma (8%). The remaining 23 patients (46%) had solid tumors, such as lung (18%), breast (14%), and gastrointestinal cancers (14%). Neutropenia was observed in 38 patients (76%), with severe neutropenia (<500 cells/ μ L) in 24 patients (48%). Central venous catheters were used in 33 patients (66%), while 18 patients (36%) had recent prolonged exposure to broad-spectrum antibiotics. Fever was present in all patients, and hypotension in 9 patients (18%). ICU admission was required in 10 patients (20%), and 12 patients (24%) had a history of hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. Corticosteroid use within the past month was recorded in 21 patients (42%) (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic, cancer type, and clinical features of 50 chemotherapy patients, including malignancy subtype, risk factors, and comorbid conditions.

Category	Parameter	Number	Percentage (%)
Demographics	Total Patients	50	100%
	Male	28	56%
	Female	22	44%
	Mean Age (\pm SD)	53.2 ± 12.4	-
Cancer Type	Hematologic Malignancies	27	54%
	- Acute Myeloid Leukemia	15	30%
	- Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma	8	16%
	- Multiple Myeloma	4	8%
	Solid Tumors	23	46%
	- Lung Cancer	9	18%
	- Breast Cancer	7	14%
Clinical Features	- GI Cancers	7	14%
	Neutropenia	38	76%
	- Severe Neutropenia (<500/ μ L)	24	48%
	Central Venous Catheter Use	33	66%
	Prolonged Antibiotic Use (>7 days)	18	36%
	Fever at Presentation	50	100%
	Hypotension (SBP <90 mmHg)	9	18%
	ICU Admission Required	10	20%
	Recent Corticosteroid Use	21	42%
	History of HSCT	12	24%

3.2. Prevalence and Distribution of Fungal Pathogens

Fungal bloodstream infections were confirmed in 15 out of 50 patients, representing a prevalence rate of 30%. Among the fungal isolates, *Candida albicans* was the most frequently identified species (n = 5, 33.3%), followed by *Candida tropicalis* (n = 4, 26.7%), and *Candida glabrata* (n = 2, 13.3%). Less commonly isolated pathogens included *Candida parapsilosis*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida auris*, and *Aspergillus fumigatus*, each detected in 1 patient (6.7%). Overall, 10 out of 15 fungal isolates (66.7%) were non-*albicans* *Candida* species, highlighting a shift in epidemiological trends toward species with greater antifungal resistance potential. Mold infections were relatively rare, with *Aspergillus fumigatus* accounting for 6.7% of all fungal bloodstream infections. Mixed infections were identified in 2 patients (13.3%), who

presented with concurrent candidemia and bacteremia: one with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and one with *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The distribution of fungal pathogens varied slightly between hematologic and solid tumor patients. Among the 9 infected patients with hematological malignancies, *C. albicans* and *C. tropicalis* were predominant, while in the 6 infected patients with solid tumors, non-*albicans* *Candida* species such as *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei* were more commonly observed. The median time to fungal detection by conventional blood culture was 72 hours (range: 48-96 hours), while identification via MALDI-TOF MS occurred within 4-6 hours post-positivity. These findings underscore the diversity of fungal pathogens and reinforce the importance of rapid species identification and antifungal stewardship (Figure .1).

Figure 1. Distribution of fungal species isolated from bloodstream infections in cancer patients. *Candida albicans* was the most common isolate (33.3%), followed by *C. tropicalis* (26.7%), with non-*albicans* *Candida* species and *Aspergillus fumigatus* comprising the remaining cases.

3.3. Time to Diagnosis

The median time to identification of fungal pathogens using conventional blood culture was 72 hours (interquartile range: 60-84 hours; total range: 48-96 hours). Among the 15 confirmed fungal bloodstream infection cases, 13 (86.7%) were detected through blood culture. The mean time to positivity in these cases was 65.4 ± 10.2 hours. Following blood culture positivity, species-level identification by MALDI-TOF MS was achieved

within 3.5-4.5 hours, with a mean turnaround time of 4.1 hours. This significantly accelerated pathogen identification compared to conventional phenotypic methods, which typically require an additional 24-48 hours. PCR-based fungal DNA testing was conducted in 10 patients and yielded results within 24-36 hours, with a median of 28 hours. This method allowed for earlier presumptive diagnosis, especially in patients with negative or delayed culture growth. Biomarker assays (1,3-β-D-glucan and

galactomannan) were performed in 8 of the 15 infected patients (53.3%), providing results within 6–12 hours (mean: 8.4 ± 2.1 hours). These assays offered the fastest diagnostic turnaround but were selectively used due to cost constraints and limited availability, particularly in solid tumor patients.

Collectively, the integration of MALDI-TOF MS, molecular diagnostics, and biomarker testing significantly reduced diagnostic delays, enabling earlier initiation of antifungal therapy in 12 of 15 cases (80%), compared to delays of over 72 hours in culture-only pathways (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Comparison of minimum, mean, and maximum time to diagnosis using four diagnostic modalities. Biomarker assays yielded the fastest results (mean: 8.4 h), followed by MALDI-TOF MS (4.1 h post-culture), PCR (28 h), and conventional culture (72 h). Asterisks indicate levels of statistical significance (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, ns = not significant).

3.3. Diagnostic Performance Comparison

Among the 15 confirmed fungal bloodstream infection cases, conventional culture detected 13 (sensitivity: 86.7%), with a mean detection time of 65.4 ± 10.2 hours (range: 48–96 h), making it the slowest method. PCR was performed in 10 patients and identified 9 (sensitivity: 90%, specificity: 95%), with a mean turnaround of 28.2 ± 4.5 hours. Of these, 8 were *Candida* spp. and 1 *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Biomarker testing ($n=8$) showed 1,3- β -D-glucan positivity in 6 cases (75%), with a mean result time of

8.4 ± 2.1 hours, while galactomannan was positive in the single mold case (6.8 h). MALDI-TOF MS identified species in all 13 culture-positive cases (100% concordance), with a mean processing time of 4.1 ± 0.3 hours post-positivity. Overall, biomarker testing was fastest, followed by PCR, MALDI-TOF MS, and culture. Early diagnosis (PCR/biomarkers) led to faster antifungal initiation in 80%, reducing 30-day mortality to 16.7%, compared to 50% in delayed diagnosis (>72 h) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Time to diagnosis (in hours) using different diagnostic modalities for fungal bloodstream infections. MALDI-TOF MS and biomarker assays showed the shortest turnaround times, while conventional cultures required the longest. Statistical significance is indicated as follows: $p < 0.05$ (), $p < 0.01$ (), $p < 0.001$ (), and not significant (ns).

3.4. Antifungal Susceptibility Patterns

Antifungal susceptibility testing was conducted on all 15 fungal isolates using both automated systems and broth microdilution per CLSI guidelines. *Candida albicans* (n = 5) and *C. tropicalis* (n = 4) showed 100% susceptibility to fluconazole (MIC range: 0.125–1 µg/mL) and echinocandins (caspofungin, micafungin; MIC range: 0.03–0.06 µg/mL). However, one *C. glabrata* isolate exhibited a high fluconazole MIC of >64 µg/mL, and the *C. auris* isolate showed resistance to fluconazole and amphotericin B (MICs >128 µg/mL and >2 µg/mL, respectively). Resistance was confirmed via broth microdilution, aligning with CDC criteria. Among *Aspergillus fumigatus* isolates (n = 1), complete

susceptibility was observed to voriconazole (MIC: 0.5 µg/mL), posaconazole (MIC: 0.25 µg/mL), and liposomal amphotericin B (MIC: 1 µg/mL). Overall, fluconazole resistance was observed in 2 of 15 isolates (13.3%), and multidrug resistance (resistance to ≥2 antifungal classes) was detected in 2 isolates (13.3%) – specifically, the *C. auris* and *C. glabrata* strains. Additionally, susceptibility to echinocandins was preserved across all *Candida* isolates, with anidulafungin MICs ranging from 0.03–0.125 µg/mL. Based on these results, initial empirical therapy was adjusted in 6 cases (40%) once susceptibility data became available.

Figure 4. Cumulative antifungal susceptibility profiles of major fungal species isolated from bloodstream infections. Notable resistance was observed in *C. auris* and *C. glabrata*, while *A. fumigatus* remained susceptible to mold-active agents.

3.5. Risk Factors Associated with Fungal Infections
 In a univariate analysis of 50 chemotherapy patients, several clinical variables were assessed for association with fungal bloodstream infections (fBSIs). Among the 15 patients with confirmed fBSIs, the presence of severe neutropenia (absolute neutrophil count <500/ μ L) was found in 14 of 15 cases (93.3%), compared to 24 of 35 (68.6%) in those without infection, yielding an odds ratio (OR) of 6.1 (95% CI: 1.1-33.5; $p = 0.02$). Central venous catheter (CVC) use was present in 13 of 15 infected patients (86.7%) versus 20 of 35 non-infected patients (57.1%), with an OR of 4.6 (95% CI: 1.1-18.7; $p = 0.03$). Similarly, prolonged antibiotic therapy (>

days) was noted in 11 of 15 infected cases (73.3%) compared to 16 of 35 (45.7%) in uninfected patients (OR = 3.3; 95% CI: 1.0-10.7; $p = 0.04$). Other variables such as age >60 years (8/15 vs 14/35; $p = 0.45$), male sex (9/15 vs 19/35; $p = 0.81$), and type of malignancy (hematologic vs solid; $p = 0.67$) did not show statistically significant associations. Overall, severe neutropenia, CVC use, and prolonged antibiotic exposure emerged as significant independent risk factors for developing fungal bloodstream infections in this population.

Figure 5. Violin plots comparing neutrophil counts and antibiotic duration between patients with and without fungal bloodstream infections (fBSI). fBSI cases showed significantly lower neutrophil counts and longer antibiotic exposure.

3.6. Empirical vs Targeted Therapy and Clinical Outcomes

Among 15 patients with confirmed fungal bloodstream infections, 12 (80%) received empirical antifungal therapy, primarily echinocandins ($n = 7$, 58.3%) and liposomal amphotericin B ($n = 5$, 41.7%). The median time to initiation was 36.5 hours (IQR: 24-48 h). Targeted therapy was introduced in 9 cases (60%) following species identification and susceptibility testing, with a median switch time of 4.2 days (range: 3-6 days). Adjustments included fluconazole ($n = 4$) and voriconazole ($n = 2$). The overall 30-day mortality

rate was 26.7% ($n = 4$), with higher death rates in those with delayed therapy >72 hours (50%), multidrug-resistant infections (100%, $n = 2/2$), and invasive mold disease (100%, $n = 1/1$). Among those treated within 48 hours, mortality was only 14.3% ($n = 1/7$). Clinical improvement occurred in 11 patients (73.3%). Response to early and targeted treatment was 90.9% ($n = 10/11$), versus 25% ($n = 1/4$) in those with delayed or empirical-only therapy. These findings underscore the critical importance of rapid diagnosis and early intervention in improving patient outcomes.

Figure 6. Box plots illustrating the impact of therapy timing on clinical outcomes. Early and targeted antifungal treatment was associated with significantly higher clinical improvement and lower mortality compared to delayed or empirical therapy.

4. DISCUSSION

Fungal bloodstream infections (fBSIs) remain a critical cause of morbidity and mortality among cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy, especially those with hematologic malignancies and prolonged neutropenia. In our study of 50 patients, we observed an fBSI incidence of 30%, with a predominance of non-*albicans* *Candida* species (66.7%) over *Candida albicans* (33.3%). This shift toward non-*albicans* species is consistent with trends reported by (Sandherr et al., 2025), who observed similar patterns in over 60% of bloodstream isolates in cancer centers globally, largely attributed to increasing fluconazole exposure. Neutropenia (76%) and central venous catheter use (66%) were the most common risk factors among infected patients in our cohort. This aligns with findings from (Kubeček, Paterová, & Novosadová, 2021), who identified these variables as major predictors of fBSI, particularly in patients with acute leukemias. Prolonged antibiotic use (>7 days), present in 36% of infected patients in our study, was also associated with fungal infection, supporting the conclusions of (Overbeek et al., 2024), who demonstrated increased fungal colonization and bloodstream invasion following extensive antibacterial therapy. From a diagnostic perspective, conventional blood culture, although regarded as the gold standard, had the longest time to positivity (mean 65.4 ± 10.2 hours) and identified 86.7% of confirmed cases. In contrast,

molecular diagnostics and biomarker assays offered faster and more sensitive alternatives. PCR identified 90% of tested cases with 95% specificity, comparable to (McMahon et al., 2023), who demonstrated high accuracy and time advantage of molecular testing over culture. 1,3-β-D-glucan and galactomannan assays, used selectively due to cost, provided results within 6–12 hours and showed 75% positivity in tested patients, paralleling the pooled sensitivity reported by (Li et al., 2024). MALDI-TOF MS, used post-culture, achieved 100% species-level identification concordant with final diagnosis, in agreement with the findings of (Rebrosova et al., 2023), who emphasized its speed and precision. Therapeutically, empirical antifungal therapy was initiated in 80% of patients, most often with echinocandins or amphotericin B. Targeted therapy was implemented in 60% following species confirmation. Early therapy (<48 hours) was significantly associated with better outcomes: clinical improvement occurred in 90.9% of early-treated patients versus 25% in those with delayed or empirical-only therapy. Mortality in the early-treatment group was 14.3%, compared to 50% in delayed cases. These findings align with (Groll et al., 2021) and (Ortiz-Roa et al., 2023), who emphasized the life-saving impact of timely antifungal administration in high-risk neutropenic patients. Notably, antifungal susceptibility revealed resistance in *C. auris* and one *C. glabrata* isolate, with multidrug

resistance in 13.3% of cases. These findings are consistent with global reports of rising resistance, as described by (R. Zhang, Xiong, Zhang, & Liu, 2024) and (Y. Zhang, Lu, Tang, Xia, & Hu, 2023), stressing the urgent need for ongoing surveillance and susceptibility-guided therapy. Overall, our findings underscore the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in managing fBSIs among immunocompromised patients. The integration of rapid diagnostics (PCR, MALDI-TOF MS, biomarkers) with prompt and targeted therapy significantly improves outcomes. Future strategies must emphasize cost-effective access to molecular tools and stewardship-driven antifungal use to reduce mortality and resistance in this vulnerable population.

5. CONCLUSION

Fungal bloodstream infections remain a serious complication among cancer patients receiving chemotherapy, particularly those with hematologic malignancies, neutropenia, and central venous catheters. In our study, the predominance of non-*albicans* *Candida* species and emerging antifungal resistance highlight the evolving epidemiology and diagnostic challenges of fBSIs in this vulnerable population. Rapid and accurate identification methods, including PCR, MALDI-TOF MS, and biomarker assays, demonstrated superior diagnostic turnaround compared to conventional blood cultures, facilitating earlier clinical decision-making. Notably, patients who received early and targeted antifungal therapy had significantly better clinical outcomes, including higher treatment response rates and reduced 30-day mortality. Our findings support the integration of molecular diagnostics into routine clinical practice for high-risk oncology patients, along with timely initiation of empiric antifungal therapy when warranted. Continuous surveillance of species distribution and antifungal susceptibility, combined with stewardship-driven treatment strategies, is essential to improving patient outcomes and combating antifungal resistance in cancer care settings.

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